

D7.1. PEDR – Plan for the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results

WP	7	Dissemination and Communication
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Dissemination Level ¹	PU	Delivery date	29/10/2021
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Lead beneficiary	UdG
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Topic manager approval	Name, date and signature
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Grant agreement 886519

ITD/IADP/TA AIR ITD

Project Acronym BEDYN

Project Title *Development of a methodology (test, measurement, analysis) to characterize the BEhaviour of composite structures under DYNamic loading*

¹Dissemination Level: **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU), **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU), **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

LIST OF VERSIONS

Version	Issue date	Changes	Author (affiliation)	Reviewer (affiliation)
01	29/10/2020	Initial outline	Emilio V. Gonzalez (UdG)	José Alfonso Artero (UC3M) José Gonzalez (COMPOXI) Vincent Jacques (DA)

LIST OF ASSOCIATED DOCUMENTS

Name	Type	Author (affiliation)

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No. 886519. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Clean Sky 2 JU members other than the Union

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ABBREVIATIONS

APC	Article Processing Charges
DA	Dassault Aviation
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
GA	Grant Agreement
ITD	Integrated Technology Demonstrators
JU	Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking
OA	Open Access
ORE	Open Research Europe publishing platform
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
UdG	Universitat de Girona
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document, *D7.1. PEDR – Plan for the Communication Dissemination and Exploitation of Results*, is a deliverable of the BEDYN project launched under the ITD, funded by the European Union's H2020 through Clean Sky 2 Programme under the Grant agreement 886519.

The aim of BEDYN project is to address a methodology to properly characterize the dynamic behaviour up to rupture of thermoset polymer-based composite structures submitted to dynamic loading. Different main objectives can be identified:

- Ob. 1) Define a modelling approach for dynamic loading events, suited to industrial needs for emergency situations applications.
- Ob. 2) Define dynamic tests, which include the definition of: specimens, test setups, and data reduction methods. Three different specimen levels are set: "coupon", for characterizing basic properties of the composite material (ply), interlaminar (delamination) and adhesive interfaces; "element", they include what can be understood as small size demonstrator (under this category the response of the flexural, notch effects and bearing will be analysed); "structure", they are devoted for characterizing the behaviour at a subcomponent level under out-of-plane dynamic loads. In order to describe properly the possible dynamic effect in some material/structure behaviours, a quasi-static test campaign is also considered for any of the specimen levels accounted for.
- Ob. 3) Define a calibration and validation process of the Finite Element Analysis (FEA) models.
- Ob. 4) Demonstrate and evaluate the proposed methodology based on tests performed.

The BEDYN project will contribute towards the consolidation of the use of numerical simulation in the design phase of polymer-based composite structures under dynamic loading. The BEDYN project will address innovative technologies, allowing better product development thanks to an increased knowledge of the behaviour of composite materials under dynamic loading. Maturing and validation of technologies is a key aspect of integrating research in the development process of industrial activities and next generation aircrafts.

CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVE	6
2. FUNDING PROGRAM ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	6
3. BEDYN COMPLETED ACTIVITIES	7
3.1. Summary of activities.....	7
3.2. Details of remarkable activities	11
3.2.1. Project logo	11
3.2.2. Project templates.....	12
3.2.3. Project webpage and LinkedIn account.....	13
3.2.4. BEDYN Community at ZENODO’s platform	13
4. BEDYN PLANNED ACTIVITIES	14
4.1. Communication.....	14
4.2. Dissemination	14
4.2.1. Open access to Peer-Reviewed papers.....	14
4.2.2. Peer-Reviewed journal articles	16
4.2.3. Conferences	17
4.3. Exploitation Plan	17
4.3.1. Exploitation Management	18

1. INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVE

Along with a project investigation, it is equally important to communicate and disseminate the project and its outputs to a target audience, and to exploit the project results. Dissemination of results mainly targets sharing the scientific results with potential users like research communities, industries etc. The process of sharing results targets raising awareness of the project, its objectives, and the problem under concern. Further, exploitation of results refers to the usage of the findings of the current project by potential users to create a product or to continue with a research question. Exploitation and dissemination of results will be performed strictly ensuring the Intellectual Property (IP) rights defined between the consortium partners, as defined in Section 8 of the Implementation Agreement.

The BEDYN Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (PEDR) aims to frame a dedicated Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation plan of the results generated in the project such as to maximise the project’s visibility and promote the project to the target audience, thus boosting the impact of the project. This document will be updated during the course of the project and all the plans proposed will be updated when they are carried out.

For the development of the current deliverable, the guidelines spread by the CS2 JU concerning Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation have been considered. For more details, see the link: https://www.cleansky.eu/sites/default/files/inline-files/DE-Webinar-29_06_21_final_en.pdf

2. FUNDING PROGRAM ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

For all the communication and dissemination activities, the acknowledgment of the funding program is referenced according to the rules of Horizon 2020 (Art. 29.4 GA). Figure 1 shows the associated logos and the sentences used.

Figure 1. Funding program acknowledgement.

3. BEDYN COMPLETED ACTIVITIES

3.1. Summary of activities

A summary of the activities carried out of Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation of Results are summarized in Table 1. The activities are listed from the newest to the oldest activity.

Table 1. Summary of the activities carried out. *Note: Communication (C), Dissemination (D) and Exploitation of Results (E).

Activity description	URL	*Type	Date	Member
Post of BEDYN project in different social networks	LinkedIn of BEDYN Twitter of AMADE research LinkedIn of AMADE research team	C	October 27, 2021	UdG
Tweet at LSD-UC3M Research Team Twitter profile: Communication of the current testing campaign 	https://twitter.com/Dynamics_uc3m/status/1451123829309427718	C	October 21, 2021	UC3M
Send detailed information of the BEDYN project activities to a journalist to generate an article with a description of the project in the magazine of the Official College of Industrial Engineers of Catalonia (Spain), demarcation in Girona (https://www.eic.cat/). Expected month of publication: November 2021	NA	C	October 14, 2021	UdG
Apply for the Annual Monographic of AEMAC journal (Spanish Association on Composite Materials), to be published on January 2022. Title: "AEMAC's contributions to the development of composite materials in Europe" 	https://mailchi.mp/aemac/bol-etn-n6-aemac-octubre-13379247?e=5972fff14a	C, D	July 6, 2021	UdG
Full communication must be sent before 30 November 2021.				
Creation of a LinkedIn account for BEDYN project. Profile: "BEDYN CS2 EU Project". Associated email: bedyn.amade@udg.edu	https://www.linkedin.com/in/bedyndyn-cs2-eu-project-78382a216/	C	June 21, 2021	UdG
Participation at "V Conference of Pre-doctoral Researchers of the UdG", performed at the Law School of the Universitat de Girona. Organized by the Doctorate School of the Universitat de Girona.	https://twitter.com/JoDoc_UdG	C, D	June 16, 2021	UdG

<p>The communication with a summary of the project thesis was sent on April 2021. Speaker: Sr. Pablo Villarroel, PhD student linked to BEDYN project.</p>				
<p>Participation in “JEC Composites - Connect” online conference 2021. https://www.jeccomposites-connect.events/</p>	<p>https://www.jeccomposites-connect.events/jcc-exhibitors-list.pdf</p>	<p>C, D</p>	<p>June 1-2, 2021</p>	<p>UdG</p>
<p>Tweet at AMADE Research Team Twitter profile: communication of a news at the Universitat de Girona related to BEDYN</p>	<p>https://twitter.com/amade_udg/status/1388066943735930880?s=20</p>	<p>C</p>	<p>April 30, 2021</p>	<p>UdG</p>
<p>Publication of a new with the description of the project on the official website of the University of Girona:</p>	<p>https://www.udg.edu/es/udg/detail-noticies/eventid/16000</p>	<p>C</p>	<p>April 27, 2021</p>	<p>UdG</p>
<p>Conference: <i>Clean Sky 2 technology progress - contribution to the environmental performance of the next generation of aircraft.</i> Organized by: Aernnova, UC3M and ASD Lab. <i>E.2 - Development of a methodology (test, measurement, analysis) to characterize the behaviour of composite structures under dynamic loading.</i> Speaker: Dr. José Alfonso Artero (UC3M)</p>	<p>file:///C:/Users/emili/Downloads/Clean_Sky_2_technology_conference_programme.pdf</p>	<p>D</p>	<p>March 24 - 25, 2021</p>	<p>UdG – UC3M</p>

<p>G.1 - Experimental and numerical analysis of composite materials and bonded joints in the framework of the CleanSky 2 program. Speaker: Dr. Carlos Sarrado (UdG)</p>				
<p>Tweet at LSD-UC3M Research Team Twitter profile: Communication for Clean Sky conference</p>	<p>https://twitter.com/Dynamics_uc3m/status/1374659165503766528</p>	<p>C</p>	<p>March 24, 2021</p>	<p>UC3M</p>
<p>Tweet at LSD-UC3M Research Team Twitter profile: Communication of the project</p>	<p>https://twitter.com/Dynamics_uc3m/status/1367396842519068673</p>	<p>C</p>	<p>March 4, 2021</p>	<p>UC3M</p>
<p>Application to participate in: European Researchers' Night ERN, initiative within the program H2020-MSCA-Night, to be held in September 2021. Each European project have an "EU-Corner", which is a window to show the projects: http://www.lanitdelarecerca.cat/</p>	<p>https://lanitdelarecerca.cat/european-corner/</p>	<p>C, D</p>	<p>February 19, 2021 September 24, 2021</p>	<p>UdG</p>
<p>New at AMADE Research Team website: BEDYN is currently running!</p>	<p>http://amade.udg.edu/index.php/2021/02/14/news-bedyn/</p>	<p>C</p>	<p>February 14, 2021</p>	<p>UdG</p>

<p>News on LSDG Lightweight Structure Dynamics Group (UC3M) website: https://www.dynamicsuc3m.com/</p>	<p>https://www.dynamicsuc3m.com/projects/296</p>	<p>C, D</p>	<p>February 08, 2021</p>	<p>UC3M</p>
<p>Creation of an account of BEDYN project in ZENODO ("Community"): European Commission co-funded multi-disciplinary repository under open license terms. Used for sharing BEDYN deliverables and results. https://zenodo.org/</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/communities/bedyn/</p>	<p>C, D</p>	<p>February 02, 2021</p>	<p>UdG</p>
<p>Description of the BEDYN project at AMADE Research Team website:</p>	<p>http://amade.udg.edu/index.php/bedyn/</p>	<p>C, D</p>	<p>January, 2021</p>	<p>UdG</p>
<p>Creation and publication of the project logo:</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>C, D</p>	<p>January, 2021</p>	<p>UdG, UC3M and COMPOXI</p>

<p>Presentation of BEDYN project in “Jornada de AEMAC – III Edición”, Spanish Association on Composite Materials. Speaker: Dr. Carlos Sarrado. Title of the talk: “Nuevos desarrollos en el análisis de materiales compuestos y uniones adhesivas”</p>	<p>https://www.aemac.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/III-Ed.-Jornada-Colaboraci%C3%B3n-AEMAC_AgendaPatrocinio.v4.pdf</p>	<p>C, D</p>	<p>November 19, 2020</p>	<p>UdG</p>
<p>Tweet at AMADE Research Team Twitter profile: start of BEDYN, Kick Off Meeting at Girona</p>	<p>https://twitter.com/amade_udg/status/1314317243715641348?s=20</p>	<p>C</p>	<p>October 8, 2020</p>	<p>UdG</p>

3.2. Details of remarkable activities

At the following sections, some of remarkable activities carried out are explained in detail.

3.2.1. Project logo

A dedicated project logo has been designed and shared in January 2021. It is the reference image to be used at any communication and dissemination activity, including all the related deliverables in BEDYN Grant Agreement. The logo contains the project acronym, where *BED* represents a projectile, and *YN* a target impacted, such as a composite laminate.

Figure 2. BEDYN’s project logo.

3.2.2. Project templates

BEDYN templates for Word reports (Figure 3) and PowerPoint (Figure 4) presentations have been created and shared among the consortium members. They will be used for both internal and external activities to identify and promote the outcomes of the project.

Figure 3. BEDYN template for project reports, first and second pages (Microsoft Word file, .docx).

Figure 4. BEDYN template for project presentations (Microsoft PowerPoint file, .pptx): first slide (left), common slide (centre), last slide (right).

3.2.3. Project webpage and LinkedIn account

The project webpage is contained in the AMADE research team website, with the path: *Research > Projects > BEDYN*. The URL is: <http://amade.udg.edu/index.php/bedyn/>.

The current content of the webpage is just a short description of the project, with the details of the funding program. Additional information is possible to be added, including submenus if desired (e.g. include the link to the associated public repository for sharing data and results).

Figure 5. BEDYN's webpage.

On the other hand, a LinkedIn account has been created for the BEDYN project. LinkedIn is a suitable platform for posting communications about the results developed directly to the target audience, and therefore, maximise the project's visibility:

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/bedyn-cs2-eu-project-78382a216/>

3.2.4. BEDYN Community at ZENODO's platform

ZENODO is a public repository recommended by Clean Sky JU for depositing any of the publications generated in the project, i.e. Open Access Peer-Reviewed papers and others, as well as Open Access Research Data. The URL associated with the BEDYN Community is:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/bedyn/>

4. BEDYN PLANNED ACTIVITIES

The list of associated activities carried out will be reported in the BEDYN Funding and Tenders Portal: *Publications* tab, *Dissemination and Communication* tab, and *Open Data* tab. In addition, WP7 has a second deliverable called *D7.2-Summary of the dissemination and communication actions*, at which all the associated activities performed during the BEDYN project will be summarized.

4.1. Communication

During the course of the project, communication activities such as those that have been achieved so far will be carried out (see Table 1). It is worth mentioning that any dissemination activity finished will be used as a topic for communication activity. Some of the expected communication activities are:

- News release in the consortium member's webpages about the progress and important milestones.
- A new publication or a participation in a conference will be posted by the responsible consortium member and the other partners should re-share it in their webpages.
- Sharing the above news in social media platforms like LinkedIn and Twitter.
- With the rights from the Topic Manager, informative images and videos could be posted in the webpage or shared in the social media.

4.2. Dissemination

Dissemination is an important set of activities contained in the BEDYN project as any other funded Horizon 2020 project. Since most of the tasks to be carried out in BEDYN are activities of research and the obtention of results, dissemination activities are and will be continuously developed and shared when possible.

4.2.1. Open access to Peer-Reviewed papers

From 2020 onwards, all European calls for research grants urge researchers to publish in Open Access and to offer openly the data used in the research object of the project funded. According to the Horizon 2020 rules, two lines of publication can be identified (see Figure 6): one set of publications are those like technical papers, conference papers, thesis and dissertations, etc.; the other corresponds to Peer-Reviewed papers, and according to the Art. 29.2 of the GA it is compulsory to publish them as Open Access.

Two main ways to apply Open Access to a publication can be considered (see Horizon 2020 guidelines):

- Open Access provided from a repository (on-line archive): a version of the manuscript published in a venue is deposited in a repository, and open access is provided, either immediately or after a delay (as a request from the publisher). Traditionally such way has been nicknamed "*Green OA*" or "*self-archiving*".
- Open access provided from the publisher's site (journal or platform): immediate open access is provided by the publisher and costs (if any e.g. Article Processing Charges - APC) are covered via

authors, funding bodies or institutions. Traditionally such way has been nicknamed “Gold OA” or “open access publishing”.

Figure 6. Scientific publications (for more details, click on [source](#)).

At the Universitat de Girona a guideline of the institutional mandate was approved in 2020 for that purpose: to evolve towards fully Open Access from 2021. Recently, the Universities that are part of the *Conferencia de Rectores de las Universidades Españolas* (CRUE; <https://www.crue.org/>) and the *Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas* (CSIC, <https://www.csic.es/en>) can publish their articles in Open Access at no additional cost to the author. The agreement is with the publishers: *Elsevier*, *Springer*, *Wiley* and *American Chemical Society* - ACS, and it means that authors who choose to publish in Open Access do not have to pay APC to the eligible journals. The agreement started on 1st January 2021, and the consortium members of the BEDYN, Universitat de Girona and Universidad Carlos II de Madrid, are part of the CRUE. Accordingly, the Peer-Reviewed papers resulting from BEDYN activities will be “Gold OA” by default.

On the other hand, research data will be shared when possible, always under the agreement of the BEDYN Topic Manager. The flow chart that will be considered is the one shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Research data (for more details, click on [source](#)).

4.2.2. Peer-Reviewed journal articles

As noted in Section 4.2.1, Peer-Reviewed journal articles resulting from BEDYN will be “GOLD OA”. Since the activities associated with the BEDYN project are basically of research, the project has the participation of different pre-doctoral students registered in the corresponding Doctorate Schools of the Universitat de Girona and Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, and supervised by senior researchers of the BEDYN project. Accordingly, most of the expected Peer-Reviewed publications will be linked with the proposed Ph.D. projects. A rough list of the expected publications is summarized in Table 2. The publication of all these proposed papers will be always under the agreement of the BEDYN’s Topic Manager. Table 3 lists some of the journals in which the work carried out in the project may be published.

It is worth mentioning that Open Research Europe (ORE) publishing platform is not considered in BEDYN for publishing scientific papers resulting from the activity of research of the pre-doctoral students. The publication by means of this platform is currently not valid by the Doctorate Schools for presenting theses in the modality of compendium of papers. However, the ORE publishing platform will be considered as an option for other possible publications.

Finally, thesis and dissertations are considered student work and are not Peer-Review (see Figure 6).

Table 2. List of proposed Peer-Review journal articles. *Note**: PVI, pre-doctorate student Sr. Pablo Villarroel (Ph.D. title: “Numerical modelling and experimental behaviour of delamination and adhesive joints under dynamic loading”); ACI, pre-doctorate student Sr. Adrián Cimadevilla (Ph.D. title: “Characterization and numerical modelling of intralaminar behaviour of composite materials under dynamic loading”); SME, pre-doctorate student Sr. Sergio Medina (Ph.D. title: “Experimental characterisation and numerical modelling of delamination propagation in composite laminates under high strain rate loading”).

Title of the paper	Linked to a PhD?*
“Characterization of delamination and adhesive joints failure under pure mode II dynamic crack propagation”	PVI
“Characterization of delamination and adhesive joints failure under mixed-mode dynamic crack propagation”	PVI
“Constitutive model for the description of delamination under dynamic loading”	PVI
“Adhesive joint modelling for dynamic load events”	PVI
“Characterization of energy release rate at high rate condition in fibre tensile mode: Compact Tension specimens”	ACI
“Constitutive model for the description of intralaminar behaviour under dynamic loading”	ACI
“Proposal and validation of new data reduction method to obtain mode I fracture toughness under dynamic loading”	SME
Other one/two possible papers can be associated with the definition and results of the experimental tests at <i>Element</i> type level: <i>Filled Hole Tension (FHT)</i> , <i>Filled Hole Compression (FHC)</i> , <i>Bearing</i> and <i>Flexure</i>	-

Table 3. List of journal candidates for Peer-Review publications in BEDYN project.

Journal	ISSN	Publisher	Quarter (Journal Citation Reports - JCR)	Impact Factor (2020)
<i>Composites Part B- Engineering</i>	1359-8368	ELSEVIER SCI LTD	Engineering, multidisciplinary: 1/90 (Q1) Materials Science, Composites: 1/28 (Q1)	9,078
<i>Composites Science And Technology</i>	0266-3538	ELSEVIER SCI LTD	Materials Science, Composites: 2/28 (Q1)	8,528
<i>Composites Part A- Applied Science And Manufacturing</i>	1359-835X	ELSEVIER SCI LTD	Materials Science, Composites: 3/28 (Q1) Engineering, Manufacturing: 7/50 (Q1)	7,664
<i>Composite Structures</i>	0263-8223	ELSEVIER SCI LTD	Mechanics: 11/135 (Q1) Materials Science, Composites: 9/28 (Q2)	5,407

<i>Engineering Fracture Mechanics</i>	0013-7944	PERGAMON-ELSEVIER SCIENCE LTD	Mechanics: 21/135 (Q1)	4,406
<i>International Journal of Solids and Structures</i>	0020-7683	PERGAMON-ELSEVIER SCIENCE LTD	Mechanics: 33/135 (Q1)	3,900

4.2.3. Conferences

Another way considered to disseminate results is by active participation in conferences. Table 4 and Table 5 list respectively the academic and the industrially oriented conferences in which it is expected to participate and show results of the BEDYN project.

Table 4. List of potential academic conferences to participate.

Conference	Type: national, European, international	Date	Location
ECCOMAS 2022 - 8th European Congress on Computational Methods in Applied Sciences and Engineering http://www.eccomas2022.org/frontal/default.asp	European	June 5-9, 2022	Oslo, Norway
MATCOMP - XIV Edición del Congreso Bienal de Materiales Compuestos	National (Spain)	June 21-23, 2022	Sevilla, Spain
CompTest 2022 - 11th International Conference on Composite Testing and Model Identification	International	NA, 2023	NA
ICCM23 - The 23rd International Conference on Composites https://iccm23.org/	International	July 30 – August 4, 2023	Belfast, UK

Table 5. List of potential industrially oriented conferences to participate.

Conference	Type: national, European, international	Date	Location
SAMPE Conference (SE Summit 22) at Paris, France, 202	European	March 07, 2022	Paris, France
JEC World	European	March 08-10, 2022	Paris, France

4.3. Exploitation Plan

According to the guidelines reported by Horizon 2020, the exploitation of results means “*The use of results in further research and innovation activities, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation and policy making activities.*”. So the exploitation of results implies the actual use of the results for scientific, societal, economic purposes or for policy making. All results generated during the project lifetime but also after its end. In Horizon 2020, the obligation to exploit is a responsibility of the beneficiaries on a “best efforts” approach, and Horizon 2020 encourages the use of the Research and Innovation results through third party exploitation (where appropriate). It is available the “Horizon Results Platform” which is free, and is part of the Funding and Tenders portal, available to all beneficiaries and is based on results, not on projects. Finally, the exploitation plan implies to take measures aiming to ensure exploitation of the results up to four years after the end of the project.

At this early stage of the project BEDYN, an initial exploitation routes and strategies can be identified, and will be defined in detail once the project results are generated in the coming months. At this stage, the document will be updated in agreement with the exploitation plans from the different partners of the consortium.

4.3.1. Exploitation Management

Exploitation of the results can be categorized within the various exploitable foregrounds that are listed below (see Art. 28 GA):

- a. Using them in further research activities (outside the action);
- b. Developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- c. Creating and providing a service, or
- d. Using them in standardisation activities.

Table 6 summarises an initial exploitation management plan listing the exploitable foreground, the exploitable results/interests associated and the concerned partner of the consortium, the foreseen exploitation plan along with the target sector.

Table 6. Exploitation management.

Exploitation type	Exploitable result/interest	Foreseen exploitation	Partner(s)	Target companies
a.	Test data generated during the project	The test data generated will be used for further research activities and projects	UdG UC3M	Design engineering companies, aeronautical and many other sectors such as electric vehicle and general automotive, wind energy, etc.
a. b. c. d.	<p>Definition of new experimental test methodologies, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of new specimens: shapes, dimensions, and layup. - Definition of new test set-ups: fixture systems, test instrumentation and methods for data processing. - Definition of new data reduction methods to obtain the desired material property or structure performance characterization. <p>Potential BEDYN tests to be accounted herein:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At <i>Coupon</i> level (dynamic conditions): longitudinal tension, longitudinal compression, interlaminar and bonded interface characterization, and adhesive strength characterization. - At <i>Element</i> level (quasi-static and dynamic conditions): Filled Hole Tension, Filled Hole Compression, Flexure, Compact Tension, and Bearing. 	Offer these non-conventional tests to others as technological transfer services, or parts of new research project proposals	UdG UC3M	Design engineering companies, aeronautical and many other sectors such as electric vehicle and general automotive, wind energy, etc.
a. b. c.	<p>Formulation and implementation of new constitutive models for advanced composite materials under different strain rate conditions, to be used in Abaqus/Explicit software. Two models are considered herein:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For the simulation of delamination and failure of bonded interfaces. - For the simulation of intralaminar failure. 	Offer simulation services and sale of numerical tools (constitutive subroutines)	UdG UC3M	Design engineering companies, aeronautical and many other sectors such as electric vehicle and general automotive, wind energy, etc.